

Figure S1. Various levels of Abl2 activation occur in mutant strains. The Abl2 expression levels of the mutant strains were compared with the Abl2 expression of the rSczy3 rescue strain at 24 and 48 hours post-infection with rSczy3, rSczy3S2-G543S-Q544S-S553T-F557Y and rSczy3S2-N1038S-CT9 Δ .